

D6.6 Final event report

TRANSFORM

Deliverable description

Deliverable:

Final event report

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01/01/2020

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36 months

Work Package concerned:

WP6 Sharing results and maximizing impact,

Concerned work package leader:

AEIDL

Dissemination level:

PU: Public (must be available on the website)

CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CI: Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

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Summary

Regional research and innovation plans are key drivers for local regional development. By adopting RRI approaches to their R&I policies and actions, TRANSFORM aims to achieve more open, transparent and democratic R&I ecosystems within three regional clusters (Lombardy, Catalonia and Brussels-Capital), leading toward more responsible territorial development. The implementing regional clusters have designed, tested, and disseminated three methodological frameworks (participatory research agenda setting, multi-stakeholder engagement, and citizen science) at the forefront of the planning and implementation of their S3 strategies.

Through WP6 Sharing results and maximizing impact, TRANSFORM aims to improve overall general awareness about RRI, create a dialogue between institutions dedicated to territorial development through wide dissemination of project results, dedicated to empowering diverse stakeholders to implement and/or engage with the development of RRI, promote shared learning and governance innovations.

The present Final event report provides a summary of the organisation of the TRANSFORM Final Conference “TRANSFORMing the territorial R&I governance. RRI and citizen engagement to open up regional R&I policymaking”, an event to present and further disseminate project results and outcomes and bring together RRI enablers and practitioners to share and learn from territorial RRI and citizen engagement projects and initiatives to further spread and foster the update of citizen engagement practice across Europe.

The TRANSFORM Final Conference was mainly organised by the project coordinator Bassetti Foundation (FGB), with AEIDL leading the promotion and communication activities. All project partners had an active role, presenting their activities, results and impact, and some Advisory Board members also took part in sessions.

In the following sections, the following chapters are presented in detail:

- Overview & rationale behind
- Agenda
- Speakers
- Communication

Overview & rationale behind

TRANSFORM Final Conference

Title: TRANSFORMing the territorial R&I governance. RRI and citizen engagement to open up regional R&I policymaking.

Format: Hybrid

Date & place: 1 – 2 December, Milan (Italy) + online (Zoom)

Objectives

The main objectives of the TRANSFORM Final Conference were to:

- Provide a synthesis of the main policy and practice-oriented findings of the project.
- Present project activities results and outcomes to further disseminate the project results and outcomes and to foster the exploitation of results.
- Launch Strategic Roadmaps for the implementation and support of territorial RRI through three methodologies - Participatory Research Agenda Setting , Multi-stakeholder Engagement and Citizen Science - developed by each cluster and project e-book.
- Bring together territorial RRI stakeholders to learn, share and network, presenting not only TRANSFORM as an inspirational case but also presenting CC-PES project and the mutual learning between TRANSFORM partners and our overseas partner Museum of Boston and other relevant projects, initiatives, and EU practices of citizen and stakeholder engagement in R&I processes and policies.
- Increase the visibility of the project.

The Final Conference targeted RRI enablers and practitioners – territorial policy makers, CSOs, NGOs, and academia.

A hybrid event

FGB has opted for a hybrid event with an in-person conference at the Museo Nazionale della Scienza e della Tecnologia Leonardo da Vinci in Milan, Italy, and an online event that remote participants could follow via Zoom.

Based on a series of reflections, the decision to organise a hybrid event was to respond to different needs and take into consideration external factors, such as increased energy prices and inflation, Covid-19 and flu wave, busy agendas of policymakers in December, and several RRI events taking place in the same week. Therefore, the hybrid event enabled broader participation, managed and mitigated eventual risks, and reduced environmental impact. The online conference has been fully recorded. Recordings and material (slides) from the two days will be available on the project's Youtube channel and website soon. This hybrid format has replaced the need to have both a final event and a project webinar.

Chat moderation and online attendees' participation

During the conference, the Zoom chat was administered by FGB to engage online participants, share documents/links/questions to better frame the discussion, and bridge with the offline conference. A list of relevant links was listed by FGB before the conference and then shared based on the flow of the discussion, adding also more resources when they popped up in the conversation. The chat with comments and questions was also displayed on the screens onsite at the end of each relevant session during Q&A time.

Poster session

A poster session was held during the two days of the Final Conference, giving a chance to relevant projects and initiatives working on RRI and citizen engagement topics to share their work, boost their visibility, and meet and exchange with RRI practitioners from across Europe.

A call for posters was published on the website to collect abstracts from projects and initiatives related to:

- RRI in R&I policies
- Citizen engagement for R&I policies
- Deliberation and co-design for R&I policies
- Research agenda setting with citizens
- Co-creation in R&I policies
- Citizen science for R&I policies
- Multi-stakeholder engagement for R&I policies
- Innovation in R&I governance

- Novel techniques of citizen and multistakeholder engagement for R&I policies

Five projects were selected to prepare posters, displayed and presented during the Final Conference:

- [MOSAIC](#) aims to study, prove and assess how solutions to big challenges such as leading big cities towards climate neutrality can be made possible and enhanced by actively involving all concerned actors through sound methodological approaches. In particular, MOSAIC focuses on understanding how the full role of citizens in co-innovation can be met and fairly rewarded. MOSAIC aims to study, prove and assess how solutions to big challenges such as leading big cities towards climate neutrality can be made possible and enhanced by actively involving all concerned actors through sound methodological approaches. In particular, MOSAIC focuses on understanding how the full role of citizens in co-innovation can be met and fairly rewarded.
- [BRIDGES – Building Reflexivity and response-ability Involving Different narratives of knowledGES](#). The project aims at: 1) investigating, mapping and enriching the narratives that frame Italian scientific research; 2) experimenting a pilot process of co-production of transdisciplinary research practices on soil fertility, through a series of meetings and seminars, in urban and rural environments, and some citizen science activities; 3) developing a reflective attitude and a sense of responsibility in citizens and researchers, making them aware of being a fertile resource for Italy.
- [ENJOI \(ENGagement and JOurnalism Innovation for Outstanding Open Science Communication\)](#) explores and tests engagement as a key asset of innovation in science communication distributed via media platforms, with a strong focus on journalism. Through a combination of methodologies and in collaboration with producers, target users and stakeholders of science communication, ENJOI co-creates and select a set of standards, principles and indicators (SPIs) condensed to a Manifesto for an Outstanding Open Science Communication.
- [FETA – Fair Energy Transition for All](#). The objective of the project was the elaboration of recommendations intended both for decision-makers operating at national level and for European decision-makers to render energy transition policies fairer and more inclusive in the sectors of housing and mobility. The policy recommendations were drafted by selected groups of experts in the sector of energy poverty and energy transition, building on conversations with vulnerable groups of citizens and putting their voices at the center of the entire process.

- **Participatory initiatives for transforming and developing the Italian mountains in a sustainable way:** This research project aims to provide the first comprehensive overview of local participatory initiatives in Italy, to map their contribution to sustainable development, and to speed up the engagement of local stakeholders. The main aim of the study is the one of allowing a dialogue between different forms of knowledge, starting from those who are actively acting in a transformation, trying to stress the importance of maintaining an equilibrium between these different spheres. To reach this goal, the project employed a mixed-method approach with multiple tools and different steps.

Participation

The TRANSFORM Final Conference aimed to create a space for sharing and knowledge among key stakeholders. The target audience was RRI enablers and practitioners across Europe, with a particular focus on regional public authorities, policymakers, NGOs, CSOs, the private sector, and academia working on and/or interested in territorial RRI and citizen engagement to further raise awareness about the topics, challenges and opportunities, disseminate the project results and outcomes, foster their uptake and maximise the impact.

Email invitations through direct mailing targeted more than 250 relevant contacts. Moreover, the project channels and channels of the project partners were used to further disseminate the information about the project and reach the target audience.

Overall 82 people registered for the event (both days). Due to Zoom technical problems potentially more people could have been registered (the full list of registrants on Monday and Tuesday before the final event has been erased by the system).

The conference had 61 participants in total for the two days, both online and onsite. The participants represented public authorities and policymakers at various levels including representatives of EU institutions (DG REGIO, JRC), managing and regional authorities, but also research and academia, EU networks (ERRIN, Eurocities), private sector, NGOs and CSOs.

Agenda

FGB prepared the agenda for the two-day event in cooperation with project partners. It was designed to first introduce the project by Angela Simone (FGB), TRANSFORM Project Coordinator, and give space to present the activities, results and outcomes of three regional clusters – Lombardy, Brussels-Capital and Catalonia – presented by all involved project partners (see below the agenda) and AB members (Louise Francis for Catalonia).

A session '**Engaging R&I stakeholders for TRANSFORM pilots in Catalonia and Brussels-Capital**' brought voices of local stakeholders – organisations and private sector representatives who took part in TRANSFORM pilots in Brussels-Capital and Catalonia. Chaired by Rosa Arias (SfC), Catalonia cluster leader, and Marzia Mazzonetto (BEpart), Brussels-capital leader, was an opportunity to learn from local organisations about challenges, opportunities, lessons learned, and added value the project brought to them. The discussion also revolved around concrete impacts at the local level, for involved organisations and the ecosystem and touched upon future outlooks.

The importance of **mutual learning** and the work done within TRANSFORM on shared capacity building have been presented in two sessions:

- '**Mutual learning across regions, the added value of TRANSFORM**' presented by Marzia Mazzonetto (BEpart), WP2 Framework definition, oversight and shared learning leader,
- and the **session 'Citizen engagement in the US. The project CC-PES'** presents mutual learning with TRANSFORM's overseas partner – the Museum of Science (Boston) – presented by David Sittenfeld.

A session was devoted to discussing **monitoring and evaluating territorial RRI** thanks to a dialogue between Roger Strand (UiB), WP7 leader, and Giulia Bubbolini, member of the TRANSFORM Advisory Board.

The **legacy** of the TRANSFORM project was presented at two levels – by regional clusters and the long-term impact of TRANSFORM activities at regional level by incorporating the results and lessons learned in strategic policies, programmes, R&I governance and internal processes. On the other hand, key tools to inspire further territories were launched during the conference:

- The executive summary of the **‘Strategic roadmap for the implementation and support of territorial RRI through participatory research agenda setting /multi-stakeholder engagement/citizen science within S3 priorities’** which aim to help regional public administrations who wish to enable citizens’ and R&I stakeholder engagement actions in their local policymaking. It presents the methodology, expected benefits, actions carried out, impact, and lessons learned in each cluster in a catchy and easy-to-read visual shape.
- **Project e-book**, in which TRANSFORM collected the most relevant reports, articles, and multimedia products as an interactive guide for all interested actors.

These tools will be further disseminated through project channels and channels of project partners to further maximise the results and guide other policymakers and RRI practitioners on their journey, providing concrete examples of how to implement and support territorial RRI and use the three tested methodologies.

Two sessions were dedicated to key EU initiatives, with speakers from various backgrounds working on different topics in relation to territorial RRI, deliberation and citizen engagement.

The key note speaker **Anna Berti Suman**, European Commission Joint Research Centre - Ispra (Falling Walls Science Breakthrough of the Year 2022 – Section Science Engagement, ‘Breaking the wall to Civic Evidence of Environmental Harms’) gave an inspirational speech about the work on ‘Civic Monitoring. Insights from the Sensing for Justice project’, showcasing several good practices.

Four other speakers representing EU institutions (EU Committee of Regions - Bertelsmann Stiftung, DG REGIO, JRC) and EU networks (ERRIN), presented **initiatives and experiences in citizen and R&I stakeholder engagement in territorial and R&I policymaking in EU** and shared current and upcoming development at EU level (Conference on the Future of Europe, DG REGIO -OECD pilot project engaging citizens in cohesion policy, EUTEends4Greens involving youth in social inclusion projects in Just Transition regions, quadruple helix collaboration in EU Missions, and the Open Discovery Process in the Partnerships for Regional Innovation) and discussed the potential insertion and replication of TRANSFORM experiences in their own settings.

EU H2020 TRANSFORM Final Conference

TRANSFORMing the territorial R&I governance.

RRI and citizen engagement to open up regional R&I policymaking.

1st-2nd December 2022
Milan – Online

Day 1 – 1st December

10:00 – 11:00 | Registration and welcome coffee

11:00 – 11:10 | Welcome

Angela Simone, Fondazione Bassetti and TRANSFORM Coordinator

11:10 – 11:30 | Introducing TRANSFORM

Angela Simone, Fondazione Bassetti and TRANSFORM Coordinator

11:30 – 12:00 | Keynote – “Civic Monitoring. Insights from the Sensing for Justice project”

Anna Berti Suman, European Commission Joint Research Centre - Ispra (Falling Walls Science Breakthrough of the Year 2022 – Section Science Engagement, ‘Breaking the wall to Civic Evidence of Environmental Harms’)

12:00 – 13:00 | TRANSFORM in action – Lombardy experience (Participatory Research Agenda Setting)

Presentation by Lombardy Cluster

- *Angela Simone - Bassetti Foundation and Lombardy cluster (WP3) leader*
- *Anna Pellizzone - Bassetti Foundation and TRANSFORM project manager*
- *Silvia Corbetta- Finlombarda S.p.A.*
- *Enza Cristofaro – Lombardy Region’s Directorate General for Education, Universities, Research, Innovation and Simplification*

13:00 – 14:00 | Lunch

14:00 – 15:00 | TRANSFORM in action – Catalonia experience (Citizen Science)

Presentation by Catalonia Cluster

- *Louise Francis - Mapping for Change and TRANSFORM Advisory Board member*
- *Rosa Arias - Science for Change and Catalonia cluster (WP4) leader*
- *Sergio Martínez - Area of Economic Strategy of the Catalan Government*
- *Josep Perellò – OpenSystems University of Barcelona*
- *Diana Reinoso - Science for Change*

15.00 – 16.00 | TRANSFORM in action – Brussels-Capital region experience (Multi-stakeholder engagement and design thinking for social innovation)

Presentation by Brussels-Capital region Cluster

- *Marzia Mazzonetto - BE participation and Brussels-Capital cluster (WP5) leader*
- *Maité Debry - BE participation*
- *Joaquin Landazuri – UCLouvain*
- *Jérémy Levin - Innoviris*

16.00 – 16.15 | Coffee break

16.15 – 16.35 | Citizen engagement in US. The project CC-PES

David Sittenfeld, Museum of Science (Boston)

16.35 – 16.55 | Monitoring and evaluating territorial RRI

Roger Strand, University of Bergen in dialogue with Giulia Bubbolini, CISE - Centro per l'Innovazione e lo Sviluppo Economico

16.50 | WRAP-UP of the day 1

Angela Simone, Fondazione Bassetti and TRANSFORM Coordinator

17.00 - 18.00 | Spritz up your territorial RRI!

Networking, spritz and poster session

Day 2 – 2nd December

9.30 – 9.35 | Welcome to Day 2

Angela Simone, Fondazione Bassetti and TRANSFORM Coordinator

9.35 – 9.50 | TRANSFORM Legacy

Angela Simone, Fondazione Bassetti and TRANSFORM Coordinator

9.50 – 10.10 | Mutual learning across regions, the added value of TRANSFORM

Marzia Mazzonetto, BE participation and Mutual learning (WP2) leader

10.10 – 11.00 | Engaging R&I stakeholders in regional policymaking

Roundtable with R&I stakeholders from Brussels-Capital and Catalonia pilots

- Alain Boribon, Citizenfund et RECYCLO.coop, Brussels
- María Busquets, Service for Urban Ecology, Energy Transition and Sustainability, Mollet del Vallès City Council
- Ludovic Libert, Happy Hours Market, Brussels
- Elisa Llurba i Olivé, Obstetrics and Gynaecology Service, Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau

Chair: Rosa Arias, Science for Change and Catalonia cluster (WP4) leader

11.00 – 11.15 | Coffee break

11.15 – 15.50 | Beyond TRANSFORM. Key experiences in Citizen and R&I stakeholder engagement in territorial policymaking in EU

- European democracy, citizens' participation and the role of regions and cities. The EU Committee of the Regions (CoR) - Bertelsmann Stiftung project
Anna Renkamp, Bertelsmann Stiftung
- Engaging citizens in cohesion policy. The DG REGIO – OECD pilot project
Francesco Amodeo, DG REGIO, EU Commission
- Regions and cities uptake of quadruple helix collaboration in EU Missions
Ryan Titley, European Regions Research and Innovation Network (ERRIN)
- The Open Discovery Process in the Partnerships for Regional Innovation
Ramojus Reimeris, European Commission Joint Research Centre – Sevilla

Chair: *Angela Simone*, Bassetti Foundation and TRANSFORM Coordinator

12.50 – 13.00 | Conclusion and farewell

Angela Simone, Fondazione Bassetti and TRANSFORM Coordinator

13.00 - 14.15 | Lunch and poster session

Speakers

The event brought together 25 speakers from across Europe representing various stakeholders (public authorities and policymakers at various levels from EU to local; academia, private sectors, NGOs and CSOs, EU network). The section below presents the list of all speakers categorised in two groups – internal (project partners and AB members) and external speakers).

Internal speakers

- Angela Simone - Bassetti Foundation, TRANSFORM Project Coordinator and Lombardy cluster (WP3) leader
- Anna Pellizzone - Bassetti Foundation and TRANSFORM Project Manager
- Silvia Corbetta– Finlombarda S.p.A.
- Enza Cristofaro – Lombardy Region’s Directorate General for Education, Universities, Research, Innovation and Simplification
- Louise Francis - Mapping for Change and TRANSFORM Advisory Board member
- Rosa Arias - Science for Change and Catalonia cluster (WP4) leader
- Sergio Martínez - Area of Economic Strategy of the Catalan Government
- Josep Perellò – OpenSystems University of Barcelona
- Diana Reinoso - Science for Change, TRANSFORM Project Manager
- Marzia Mazzonetto - BE participation and Brussels-Capital cluster (WP5) and WP2 leader
- Maité Debry - BE participation, TRANSFORM Project Manager
- Joaquin Landazuri – UCLouvain
- Jérémy Levin – Innoviris
- David Sittenfeld, Museum of Science (Boston)
- Roger Strand, University of Bergen, WP7 leader
- Giulia Bubbolini, CISE - Centro per l'Innovazione e lo Sviluppo Economico and TRANSFORM Advisory Board member

External speakers

Local stakeholders

- Alain Boribon, Citizenfund et RECYCLO.coop, Brussels

- María Busquets, Service for Urban Ecology, Energy Transition and Sustainability, Mollet del Vallès City Council
- Ludovic Libert, Happy Hours Market, Brussels
- Elisa Llorba i Olivé, Obstetrics and Gynaecology Service, Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau

EU level stakeholder

- Anna Berti Suman, European Commission Joint Research Centre - Ispra (Falling Walls Science Breakthrough of the Year 2022 – Section Science Engagement, ‘Breaking the wall to Civic Evidence of Environmental Harms’)
- Anna Renkamp, Bertelsmann Stiftung
- Francesco Amodeo, DG REGIO - EU Commission
- Ryan Titley, European Regions Research and Innovation Network (ERRIN)
- Ramojus Reimeris, European Commission Joint Research Centre – Sevilla

Communication

Communication strategy

The planning of the communication campaign for the final event started in July 2022 with the implementation from August to December 2022.

While FGB was in charge of the overall organisation of the event, AEIDL was responsible for the communication of the final conference, building the communication strategy, creating the visual identity, communication and promotional materials, and dissemination channels of the conference. Below you can find a table with the main actions identified with the strategy.

Action	Implementing partner(s)	Channels	Target audience
<i>Save the date</i>	AEIDL	<i>Social media</i>	<i>All</i>
<i>Open call for posters</i>	AEIDL + all partners	TRANSFORM website & social media Direct mailing, direct messages on social media (Twitter, LinkedIn) Partners' channels	RRI and citizen engagement projects
<i>Short trailer</i>	AEIDL	TRANSFORM website & social media	All
<i>Invitation</i>	AEIDL + all partners	TRANSFORM website & social media Partners' channels Direct mailing Direct messages social media	All
<i>Agenda</i>	AEIDL	TRANSFORM website Social media	All
<i>Press invite</i>	AEIDL	Anewstip TRANSFORM website	Press & media
<i>Article about the conference and outcomes</i>	AEIDL + all partners	TRANSFORM website Social media Direct mailing	All Conference participants

<i>Final conference video</i>	AEIDL	TRANSFORM website Social media Partners' channels	All
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Visual identity

AEIDL's graphic designer built the visual identity of the event in line with the visual identity of the project. To ensure consistency, the colours predominantly used for the communication and promotional materials were used, creating a modern and catchy look.

Save the date

The Save the Date for the conference was the first material produced. It showcased some important information: the title, dates, place, and format. It was distributed through social media and partners.

Figure 1: TRANSFORM Final Conference Save the Date

Website

<https://www.transform-project.eu/final-conference-2022/>

The website for the final conference – embedded in the project official website - was developed and published by AEIDL's graphic designer providing essential information about the conference logically structured into the following web pages:

Home page: information about the conference, including the date, place and link to the registration forms for both onsite and online participation. A short section promoting the open call for posters with a link to further information and a call for action (apply) was added to the bottom of the home page.

Call for posters: information about the open call for posters with information about targeted projects/initiatives and instructions on how to submit an abstract.

Agenda: detailed agenda for both days

Practical information: instructions for participants on how to get to Milan as well as to the venue and current Covid-19 restrictions in Italy.

Figure 2: TRANSFORM Final Conference - homepage

Figure 3: TRANSFORM Final Conference - call for posters

TRANSFORM Final Conference

CALL FOR POSTERS

Would you like to share your experience in territorial RRI or citizen engagement related to R&I topics and policies?

During our final conference (1st and 2nd December 2022), we welcome posters presenting practices, projects, and initiatives that deal with TRANSFORM topics and methodologies.

In particular we are interested in – even if further themes are also welcome:

- RRI in R&I policies
- Citizen engagement for R&I policies
- Deliberation and co-design for R&I policies
- Research agenda setting with citizens
- Co-creation in R&I policies
- Citizen science for R&I policies
- Multi-stakeholder engagement for R&I policies
- Innovation in R&I governance
- Novel techniques of citizen and multistakeholder engagement for R&I policies

Poster sessions will be held during the two days of the conference, with plenty of time to interact with EU stakeholders. Furthermore, posters will be displayed at the meeting venue from the beginning until the end of the conference.

Submission

Please submit your poster proposal to Lucia Princikova at lpr@aeidl.eu by providing the following information:

- Title
- Abstract: (max. 500 words) including the context, the approach/the methodology, results and policy impact
- Author(s); (name, institution, contacts)

Hurry up to secure your spot!

15 spots available. Posters will be accepted on a first-come, first-served basis.

E-mail invitation

An email invitation was created for the direct mailing distributions. A concise and visually appealing design in line with the visual identity was distributed by AEIDL and TRANSFORM partners to relevant contacts by email in line with GDPR rules. The direct mailing was sent to more than 250 relevant contacts, targeting RRI practitioners, public authorities, sister projects, other EU-funded projects dealing with citizen engagement and deliberation, deliberation and Green Deal, co-creation in twin transitions, RRI, RRI monitoring, citizens science, and relevant initiatives connected to citizen engagement and RRI also beyond Europe.

Figure 4: TRANSFORM Final Conference email invitation

The graphic is an email invitation for the TRANSFORM Final Conference. It features a header with the event title in a pink bar, dates in a teal bar, and a background image of a conference audience. The main text is in black, with key terms in pink. At the bottom, there are two buttons for registration options and a closing line from the TRANSFORM team.

TRANSFORM FINAL CONFERENCE

1 - 2 December 2022
Hybrid | Milan & Online

TRANSFORMing the territorial R&I governance.

RRI and citizen engagement to open up regional R&I policymaking.

Join the TRANSFORM Final Conference

Over the past three years, the EU H2020 **TRANSFORM** project has been exploring and experimenting with **citizen engagement** methodologies in **regional R&I governance**, dealing in particular with Smart Specialisation Strategies (S3). Under the common framework of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), three regions - Lombardy (Italy), Brussels- Capital (Belgium) and Catalonia (Spain) – run pilot actions aimed at implementing **open and inclusive processes** that make **local R&I priorities more connected to societal needs**.

As it is now coming to an end, the TRANSFORM project is organising its Final Conference.

WHEN? 1st - 2nd December 2022

WHERE? Museo Nazionale della Scienza e della Tecnologia Leonardo da Vinci, Via San Vittore 21, Milan, Italy and Online (Zoom)

The event is an opportunity to **SHARE** project results, **LEARN** from inspiring practices of citizen and R&I stakeholder engagement in territorial policymaking and key note speakers, and **DISCUSS** current and future development with stakeholders working on territorial RRI and citizen engagement from different corners of Europe. The event will be also web streamed.

Join us!

On site in Milan

Online

We look forward to seeing you in Milan.

TRANSFORM team

Call for posters

A unique opportunity to promote your own project or initiative. 15 posters will be displayed during the Conference and presented during dedicated slots of networking activities.

Check out the details, and share your abstract with us.

[Learn More](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 872687. The contents of this document are the sole responsibility of TRANSFORM consortium and can in no way be taken to reflect the views of the European Commission.

Social media

Social media channels were one of the main channels to promote the final conference. Primarily, we used the social media of the project, however, the project partners acted as multipliers to further disseminate the information through their social media but also other means (i.e newsletter, email invitations).

Visuals

Several banners were created as visual support for social media posts under the following categories.

- Promoting the final conference (two versions)
- Open call for projects (two versions)
- Cards introducing external and invited speakers and sessions (one for each speaker and panel)

All banners were available in different formats and versions for different social media – Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook. Find below some examples.

Figure 5: Twitter - open call for posters

Figure 6: LinkedIn post

Figure 7: Facebook post - final conference

Video trailer

A short video trailer (17 seconds) was created before the conference to support the outreach on social media and boost registrations. Short, snappy design in line with the visual identity of the conference, and the project, focused on essential information and included a call for action – Register now. The video has reached 245 views.

Link: https://twitter.com/TRANSFORM_eu/status/1594734525124575232

Direct messages

Direct messages on Twitter were sent to 41 relevant projects dealing with topics related to territorial RRI and citizen engagement in R&I. The messages in a more informal tone were inviting projects to participate in the conference and submit the abstract for the poster session. The messages included a link to the Final Conference website and a post made on Twitter prompting people to register.

Live-tweeting during the conference

Twitter has been very useful to live-tweet relevant quotes and key information during the conference. This has been an optimal way to get the attention of the audience. Plus, by tagging the speakers and their organisations, and thanks to their retweets and interaction, we got the possibility to reach a larger audience.

Press invitation

A press invitation informing about the conference was developed by AEIDL and sent out to the mailing list using the Anewstip database. The mailing list of outlets and journalists was built based on the following criteria:

Language: English

Location: EU countries

Keywords (pre-defined and free): Europe, Society, Science, Research, Politics, Innovation, Social Sciences

In addition, the results were screened and only the most relevant outlets and journalists were added to the mailing list. In total, the mailing list consisted of 110 contacts on 22 November. The opening rate reached 19.09%. (see below the information provided by Anewstip).

Figure 8: Anewstip analytics

Subject	Recipients	Status	Sent rate	Open rate	Clicks ⓘ	Date	Action
Join the TRANSFORM Final Conference	110 ⓘ	Sent	96.36%	19.09%	0	24 Nov 2022	🗑️ 📄

Promotional kit

A promotional kit was developed by AEIDL to 1) facilitate the communication efforts of the partners; 2) guide partners in communicating about the final conference; 3) ensure consistency in the overall communication activities.

The kit was shared with partners via email with detailed instructions and a link to the promotional kit folder stored in the shared drive of the project. The following elements were included:

- Banners in various formats (website, Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook)
- Text for social media posts (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook)
- Email invitation
- A short news article for the website

- Text for social media direct message

Figure 9: TRANSFORM Final Conference - web banner

Promotional & event materials

Several promotional and event materials were produced. In line with the sustainable events policy, the consortium minimized the use of printed and promotional materials.

A **roll-up** (for reusable roll-up holders) was designed and produced for the conference; **badges** (for reusable badge holders) for in-person participants with TRANSFORM visual identity were designed (see below). Moreover, **online cards** presenting speakers and sessions were created to be used on social media but also be displayed on the screen during the conference introducing the speakers and sessions.

Figure 10: TRANSFORM Final Conference badge

Figure 11: TRANSFORM Final Conference roll-up

TRANSFORM

FINAL CONFERENCE

TRANSFORMing the territorial R&I governance.
RRI and citizen engagement
to open up regional R&I policymaking.

1st - 2nd December

Hybrid event
Online / Milan

Organised by

TRANSFORM

Partners

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 862739

TRANSFORM

Figure 12: Online card - session overview

TRANSFORM FINAL CONFERENCE
1 - 2 DECEMBER | MILAN & ONLINE

Beyond TRANSFORM. Key experiences in Citizen and R&I stakeholder engagement in territorial policymaking in EU DAY 2 | 11:15 - 12:50

<i>European democracy, citizens' participation and the role of regions and cities</i>	<i>Engaging citizens in cohesion policy. The DG REGIO – OECD pilot project</i>	<i>Regions and cities uptake of quadruple helix collaboration in EU Missions</i>	<i>The Open Discovery Process in the Partnerships for Regional Innovation</i>
ANNA RENKAMP Bertelsmann Stiftung	FRANCESCO AMODEO EU Commission - DG REGIO	RYAN TITLEY ERRIN	RAMOJUS REIMERIS EU Commission JRC Sevilla

TRANSFORM FINAL CONFERENCE
TRANSFORMING THE TERRITORIAL R&I GOVERNANCE.
RRI AND CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT TO OPEN UP REGIONAL R&I POLICYMAKING.

KEYNOTE SPEAKER

ANNA BERTI SUMAN
European Commission Joint Research Centre - Ispra

Falling Walls Science Breakthrough of the Year 2022 – Section Science Engagement, 'Breaking the wall to Civic Evidence of Environmental Harms'

Communication outcomes

News article

A news article about the conference and its outcomes will be published on the TRANSFORM website in English.

Final conference video

The final conference was a great opportunity for all partners to meet (Due to Covid-19 only one consortium meeting was held in person), and further, convey key messages of the TRANSFORM project. AEIDL, therefore, decided to create an additional project video during the conference, giving space to project partners to present their TRANSFORMative journey, activities, benefits and impact.

Objectives

Promote territorial RRI and citizen engagement in (regional) R&I policy and governance to create policies more aligned with citizens' needs, values and aspirations.

Target audiences

- Policy makers and public authorities
- RRI practitioners

Key messages

- **Learn** from TRANSFORM's territorial RRI and citizen engagement activities and lessons learned, benefits and impact in regional R&I policymaking (illustrated on examples from 3 regional clusters)
- **Get inspired** by these examples and benefit from developed tools (replication/transfer)

Call for action

Get inspired by TRANSFORM and embark on a participation journey.

Format

A 3 minutes video showing key moments and atmosphere of the conference with short interviews of project partners on transformative potential, added value and impact of territorial RRI and citizen engagement in regional R&I policy making and governance,

conveying the message of practical examples implemented in three regional clusters in the framework of TRANSFORM.

The video will be published on the project's YouTube channel and the website and promoted on social media.

Executive summaries of Strategic roadmaps and Project e-book

The legacy of the TRANSFORM project was presented during the Final Conference through the launch of two key deliverables launched during the conference:

- The executive summary of the **'Strategic roadmap for the implementation and support of territorial RRI through participatory research agenda setting, multi-stakeholder engagement and citizen science strategies within S3 priorities'** which aim to help regional public administrations who wish to enable citizens' and R&I stakeholder engagement actions in their local policymaking. It presents the methodology, expected benefits, actions carried out, impact and lessons learned.
- **Project e-book**, in which TRANSFORM collected the most relevant reports, articles, and multimedia products as an easy-to-use guide for all interested actors.

These deliverables are now available on the project website, the links were shared in the chat during the conference and shared on Twitter.

Further dissemination of these deliverables will be done after the Final Conference through project communication channels and project partners' channels.

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 Supporting the development of territorial Responsible Research and Innovation

 TRANSFORM project

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement N° 872687

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